

Supplementary Material for
**Perceptual Study on the Plausibility of Binaural
Rendering in Anechoic Environments**

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1 Perceptual Evaluation - Additional Information

1.1 Descriptive Statistics

All results of the signal detection theory are provided as ‘Rdata’. Table 1 summarizes the descriptive values d'_{avg} and β'_{avg} , each experiment and naive and expert listeners separately.

Table 1: Descriptive statistical values of the results of all experiments.

Experiment	Participant Group	d'_{avg}	β'_{avg}
Experiment 1: baseline	All	0.31	1.12
Experiment 2: N = 44	All	0.31	1.12
Experiment 2: N = 12	All	0.49	1.37
Experiment 2: N = 7	All	0.56	1.20
Experiment 2: N = 3	All	0.94	1.76
Experiment 3: visual	All	0.57	1.31
Experiment 3: visual	Naive	0.50	1.21
Experiment 3: visual	Experts	0.65	1.41
Experiment 3: no-visual	All	0.5	1.29
Experiment 3: no-visual	Naive	0.38	1.38
Experiment 3: no-visual	Experts	0.62	1.21
Experiment 4: KU100	All	0.26	1.33
Experiment 4: KU100	Naive	0.3	1.5
Experiment 4: KU100	Experts	0.21	1.14
Experiment 4: Spherical Head	All	0.577	1.80
Experiment 4: Spherical Head	Naive	0.63	2.14
Experiment 4: Spherical Head	Experts	0.51	1.41
Experiment 5: 3 DoF	All	0.73	1.67
Experiment 5: 3 DoF	Naive	0.81	1.97
Experiment 5: 3 DoF	Experts	0.64	1.32
Experiment 5: 6 DoF	All	0.57	1.307
Experiment 5: 6 DoF	Naive	0.50	1.21
Experiment 5: 6 DoF	Experts	0.65	1.41

1.2 Analysis of Epochs

Figure S1: Experiment 2 - $N = 3$: Individual d' , average d' , and corresponding 95% CIs, as well as average bias β' and error bars with respect for epochs.

Figure S2: Experiment 2 - $N = 7$: Individual d' , average d' , and corresponding 95% CIs, as well as average bias β' and error bars with respect for epochs.

Figure S3: Experiment 2 - $N = 12$: Individual d' , average d' , and corresponding 95% CIs, as well as average bias β' and error bars with respect for epochs.

Figure S4: Experiment 2 - $N = 44$: Individual d' , average d' , and corresponding 95% CIs, as well as average bias β' and error bars with respect for epochs.

Figure S5: Experiment 3 - no-visual: Individual d' , average d' , and corresponding 95% CIs, as well as average bias β' and error bars with respect for epochs.

Figure S6: Experiment 3 - visuals: Individual d' , average d' , and corresponding 95% CIs, as well as average bias β' and error bars with respect for epochs.

Figure S7: Experiment 4 - KU100: Individual d' , average d' , and corresponding 95% CIs, as well as average bias β' and error bars with respect for epochs.

Figure S8: Experiment 4 - Spherical Head Model: Individual d' , average d' , and corresponding 95% CIs, as well as average bias β' and error bars with respect for epochs.

Figure S9: Experiment 5 - 3 DoF: Individual d' , average d' , and corresponding 95% CIs, as well as average bias β' and error bars with respect for epochs.

1.3 Analysis of Tracking Data

1.3.1 Translational Head Movements 3DoF vs 6 DoF

The folder 'tracking_data_analysis/translation.3dof_vs.6dof' contains plots for each participant separately, evaluating the translational head movements in Experiment 5. Fig. S10 shows the tracking data for participant 1 as an example. Turquoise indicates a hit and red indicates a miss for each condition.

Figure S10: Experiment 5 - 3DoF: Positions over the duration of each playback of the corresponding condition as points in steps of 200 ms. Hits are represented in turquoise, while misses are shown in red.

1.3.2 Analysis of Horizontal Head Orientation

The orientation analysis is divided into individual conditions based on the position of the loudspeaker and the type of playback. The azimuth angles of the last 1.6 seconds were averaged for each playback and then categorized as hit or miss. In each playback scenario, the orientation data were rotated based on the loudspeaker position to display the loudspeakers at 0° within the plots. As an example, Figure S11 shows the data of a single subject, where each dot represents one playback. Turquoise indicates a hit and red indicates a miss for each condition. The hits and misses have been divided into different intensity ranges for clarity. The playbacks displayed depend on the angle and a random intensity value within the defined range.

Figures S12-S13 provide an overview of the general orientation of each experiment. The hit and miss rates of each direction are shown as intensity in 1° steps and are normalized to the respective speaker position and its playback type. In contrast to the individual subject plots, the average azimuth angle over the last 1.6 seconds of each playback is not calculated. Instead, the hit rate and miss rate include the individual angles within the 1.6 seconds.

Figure S11: Experiment 2 - N44 Participant 1: Average orientation of the last few seconds for each playback of the corresponding condition are depicted as dots. The data in each plot has been rotated so that the loudspeakers are at 0° .

Figure S12: Experiment 2 - N44: The hit rate is shown in turquoise and the miss rate is shown in red for each direction in 1° steps. The data in each plot has been rotated so that the loudspeakers are at 0°.

Figure S13: Experiment 3 - no-visuals: The hit rate is shown in turquoise and the miss rate is shown in red for each direction in 1° steps. The data in each plot has been rotated so that the loudspeakers are at 0°.

Figure S14: Experiment 3 - visuals: The hit rate is shown in turquoise and the miss rate is shown in red for each direction in 1° steps. The data in each plot has been rotated so that the loudspeakers are at 0° .

Figure S15: Experiment 4 - KU100: The hit rate is shown in turquoise and the miss rate is shown in red for each direction in 1° steps. The data in each plot has been rotated so that the loudspeakers are at 0° .

Figure S16: Experiment 4 - Spherical Head Model: The hit rate is shown in turquoise and the miss rate is shown in red for each direction in 1° steps. The data in each plot has been rotated so that the loudspeakers are at 0°.

Figure S17: Experiment 5 - 3DoF: The hit rate is shown in turquoise and the miss rate is shown in red for each direction in 1° steps. The data in each plot has been rotated so that the loudspeakers are at 0°.

1.3.3 Influence of Horizontal Head Movements on Sensitivity

Figure S18: Experiment 2 - N44: Average azimuth range in which each subject moved during the test procedure in relation to their individual d' .

Figure S19: Experiment 3 - no-visuals: Average azimuth range in which each subject moved during the test procedure in relation to their individual d' .

Figure S20: Experiment 3 - visuals: Average azimuth range in which each subject moved during the test procedure in relation to their individual d' .

Figure S21: Experiment 4 - KU100: Average azimuth range in which each subject moved during the test procedure in relation to their individual d' .

Figure S22: Experiment 4 - Spherical Head Model: Average azimuth range in which each subject moved during the test procedure in relation to their individual d' .

Figure S23: Experiment 4 - 3DoF: Average azimuth range in which each subject moved during the test procedure in relation to their individual d' .

1.4 Analysis of Test Signals

Figure S24: Experiment 2 - N44: Overall hit and miss rates of each test signal for virtual and real reproduction.

Figure S25: Experiment 3 - no visual: Overall hit and miss rates of each test signal for virtual and real reproduction.

Figure S26: Experiment 3 - visuals: Overall hit and miss rates of each test signal for virtual and real reproduction.

Figure S27: Experiment 4 - KU100: Overall hit and miss rates of each test signal for virtual and real reproduction.

Figure S28: Experiment 4 - Spherical Head: Overall hit and miss rates of each test signal for virtual and real reproduction.

Figure S29: Experiment 5 - 3DoF: Overall hit and miss rates of each test signal for virtual and real reproduction.